

Separation of Metal Thiocyanato Complex Ions by Paper Electrophoresis*

H. G. MUKHERJEE, D. MAJUMDAR and S. P. NAG

Pure Chemistry Department, University College of Science, Calcutta University, Calcutta-9

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In this communication electrophoretic migration in paper of some thiocyanato-complex ions and their separations from their binary mixtures using ammonium thiocyanate as background electrolyte have been discussed.

NUMEROUS separations of cations by paper electrophoresis have been studied earlier¹. Lederer^{2,3} has separated mixtures of Fe, Co and Ni ions using alcoholic solutions of alkali thiocyanate.

Water soluble thiocyanato complex of Cr³⁺ was prepared as follows : chromic hydroxide was prepared from chromic chloride and sodium hydroxide using

standard method of preparation⁴. Less than equivalent amount of free thiocyanic acid (which was prepared from ammonium thiocyanate, lead nitrate and sulphuric acid using standard technique) was added and the filtrate was treated with excess ammonium thiocyanate. From the solution dark red crystals of (NH₄)₃ Cr(NCS)₆ were separated⁴. The standard method⁵ of preparation was followed to prepare complexes of Ag, Hg, Pb, Cd, Bi, Co, Fe and uranyl ions. But for Ni and Co, the method fails. as on keeping, the solution of these complexes decompose with separation of sulphur. So the solutions

* Read at the Convention of Chemists, 1969. (Indian Chem. Soc.).

TABLE I

Separation sequences of the binary mixtures of the thiocyanato complexes. Carrier electrolyte 0.2N NH₄CNS; 5 hrs' run under a potential diff. of 220 volts. '-' sign indicates migration towards the cathode, '+' sign indicates movement towards the anode and ':' indicates point of application.

- : Pb(NCS) ₄ ²⁻ , Ag(NCS) ₂ ⁻⁺ ;	- : Hg(NCS) ₄ ²⁻ , Ag(NCS) ₂ ⁻⁺ .
- : Pb(NCS) ₄ ²⁻ , Hg(NCS) ₄ ²⁻ +	- : Ag(NCS) ₂ ⁻ , Bi(NCS) ₆ ³⁻ +
- Ni ²⁺ : Ag(NCS) ₂ ⁻⁺ ;	- Co ²⁺ : Ag(NCS) ₂ ⁻⁺ .
- : Cd(NCS) ₄ ²⁻ , Bi(NCS) ₆ ³⁻ +	- Fe(NCS) ⁺⁺ : Bi(NCS) ₆ ³⁻ +
- Cr ³⁺ : Bi(NCS) ₆ ³⁻ +	- Co ²⁺ : Bi(NCS) ₆ ³⁻ +
- : UO ₂ (NCS) ₃ ⁻ , Bi(NCS) ₆ ³⁻ ;	- Ni ²⁺ : Bi(NCS) ₆ ³⁻ +

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF THE BACKGROUND ELECTROLYTE

Carrier electrolyte	Time	Movement of complex ions when electrophorised					
		Co ⁺⁺ anionic	Bi ⁺⁺⁺ anionic	Cd ⁺⁺ anionic	Hg ⁺⁺ anionic	UO ₂ ⁺⁺ anionic	
NH ₄ NCS(N/5)	12 hrs						
„ (N/10)	„	cationic	„	cationic	cationic	cationic	
„ (N/20)	„	„	„	„	„	„	
NH ₄ NCS(N/5)	12 hrs	Mo ⁺⁺⁺ anionic	Ni ⁺⁺ cationic	Fe ⁺⁺⁺ cationic	Cr ⁺⁺⁺ cationic	Ag ⁺ anionic	Tl ⁺ anionic
„ (N/10)	„	cationic	„	„	„	„	„
„ (N/15)	„	„	„	„	„	„	„

Developing agent : Alizarin for Cr³⁺, K₄[Fe(CN)₆] for UO₂²⁺, KI for Tl⁺, Mo³⁺ self-indicated and ammonium polysulphide for other ions.

are used *in situ*. Separations of the following thiocyanato complexes by paper electrophoretic method using 0.2N NH_4CNS solution as carrier electrolyte under a potential difference of 220 volts and after 5 hr's run have been made possible.

It has also been observed that when nitrate/chloride of metals are subjected to paper electrophoresis for 5 hrs using $N/5$ ammonium thiocyanate as background electrolyte, Co, Ni, Pb, Bi, Cu, Zn, Al, Be and UO_2^{++} ions move towards the cathode whereas Hg, Pd, Os and Au move towards the anode showing thereby that Hg, Pd, Os and Au under this condition easily form anionic complexes whereas others do not.

It has also been found that the concentration of background electrolyte has remarkable effect on the direction of migration of the thiocyanato complexes. Sometimes dilution of the background electrolyte

leads to a change in the direction of migration of the ion i.e., complex anion may dissociate into simple cation. The result obtained is as follows :

Separation sequences of the mixtures such as Ag-Pb, Ag-Hg, Pb-Hg, Ag-Bi, Ag-Ni, Ag-Co, Cd-Bi, Bi-Fe, Bi-Cr, Bi-Co, Bi-Ni and Bi- UO_2^{++} are shown in the Table.

References

1. M. LEDERER, *Chromatographic Rev.*, 1961, **3**, 15.
2. M. LEDERER and F. L. WARD, *Anal. Chem. Acta.*, 1952, **6**, 355.
3. M. LEDERER, *Nature*, 1951, **167**, 364.
4. H. G. MUKHERJEE, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1958, **163**, 408.
5. A. KAWAMURA, H. OKAMURA and N. KAMAKO, *Japan Analyst*, 1955, **4**, 158, 163 and 166.
6. H. REMY, "Treatise on Inorganic Chemistry", Vol. 2, p. 223, 286, 300, 315.